

Quantum Mechanics and Complex Numbers Part II

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In part I of this note, we argued that $\exp(ipx)$ written as a 2-vector is solution of a 2×2 rotation matrix with $\cos(p \, dx)$ like terms operating on $(a(px), b(px))$ to yield d/dx operating on this same vector i.e. the translation operator. We did not give a reason why this should be the case.

In this note, we focus on developing bound state quantum mechanics as a statistical theory in parallel with classical statistical theory. As argued in previous notes, the free particle "probability" becomes the central object because there is no acceleration in the statistical picture. It must possess an invariance related to all x points because none is preferential. Ideas of periodicity and invariance, linked to a statistical picture, seem to arise and lead to the complex periodic/spatially invariant form $\exp(ipx)$. A number of the ideas in this note have been touched upon in previous notes, but here we try to develop the ideas strictly by comparing with the classical statistical scenario and stressing spatial invariance.

Classical Statistical Mechanics

The idea of classical statistical mechanics seems to be to consider a large number of free particles which collide with each other establishing a temperature equilibrium. In the absence of a potential, one has $f(p)$ i.e. a probability to have a particular momentum. The idea of invariance in x is present through the fact $f(p)$. If a potential is added, classical mechanics suggests one should follow each particle in time, noting how it accelerates while still colliding with other particles. Statistical mechanics, however, does not take this approach. It deals with probabilities. In the case of a potential, one has $f(p, x)$, but collisions are still the creator of equilibrium at each x so:

$$f(p, x) = f(p)g(x) \quad ((1))$$

$g(x)$ then becomes a spatial density due to the potential. One may note that $f(p) > 0$ and $g(p) > 0$ (and both are real).

Quantum Bound States

Following the ideas of classical statistical mechanics, one may try to apply these to a single bound quantum particle. Immediately there is a big difference. In quantum mechanics, there is only one particle. Thus, this particle must undergo some kind of stochastic motion so that an averaging process is needed. Following classical statistical mechanics a probability is defined for a free particle:

$$F(p, x) \quad ((2))$$

For the classical case, invariance in space led to $f(p,x)=f(p)$. Can one state that $F(p,x)=F(p)$? If this were the case, creating an ensemble average for kinetic energy: $\sum \frac{p^2}{2m} a(p) F(p) / [\sum a(p) F(p)]$ would lead to an x independent result, but one should have:

$$KE(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((3))$$

This idea has already been stated in previous notes. Thus, one must have $F(p,x)$ even for a free particle, breaking with classical statistical mechanics.

A main idea in this note is that for a free particle there should be a kind of invariance associated with each x point. One cannot choose $F(p,x)=\text{constant}$ because this does not depend on x . As argued in previous notes, it seems that one requires:

$$F(p,x) = \text{periodic function in } x \quad ((4))$$

At this point, the frequency is completely unknown. We argue that a periodic function does not necessarily imply invariance in x . For example, one may have three humps in x , one larger than the other which repeat periodically. This is periodic, but not invariant because each hump treats x space differently. Thus, one needs a combination of periodicity with invariance as one moves through space, but this invariance has not yet been defined.

A major question that arises is: What should the spatial frequency of this periodicity be? Should it be independent of p ? If it is independent of p , then one needs an extra index i.e.

$$F(p,x) \text{ becomes } F(p,x,k) \text{ unless } k \text{ is the same for all } p. \quad ((4))$$

If k were the same for all p , then $F(p,x,k)$ would be separable it seems i.e. $F_1(p)F_2(x, K)$. Then:

$$KE(x) = \frac{\sum \frac{p^2}{2m} a(p) F_1(p) F_2(x, K)}{[\sum a(p) F_1(p) F_2(x, K)]}$$

$$= \frac{F_2(x, K)}{F_2(x, K)} \left[\frac{\sum \frac{p^2}{2m} a(p) F_1(p)}{[\sum a(p) F_1(p)]} \right] \quad ((5))$$

((5)), however, becomes independent of x , but $KE(x)$ so this cannot be the case. Thus, k must somehow be dependent on p . This suggests:

$F(q(p)x)$ as the periodic function with $q(p)$ being the spatial circular frequency. $q(p)=p$, however, so for a given p , one would map into a number p_1 which could be seen as representing another frequency p_1 . This seems to lead to the idea of $F(px)$. This is strengthened by the idea that a translation of $F(px)$ is related to p which is the energy flow for this scenario.

At this point, one may introduce the idea of invariance in x . It is not sufficient to have a periodic function, the function must treat all x points the same. A way to achieve this mathematically is to have a two dimensional rotation in px linked to the translation i.e

$$\begin{vmatrix} \cos(p dx) & -\sin(p dx) \\ \sin(p dx) & \cos(p dx) \end{vmatrix} \begin{vmatrix} |a(px)| \\ |b(px)| \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} |1 - p dx| & |a(px)| \\ |p dx - 1| & |b(px)| \end{vmatrix} = \frac{d/dx |a(px)|}{|b(px)|} \quad ((7))$$

As shown in Part I, $a(px)=\cos(px)$ and $b(px)=\sin(px)$ is a solution.

With a rotation, each point is on a circle and has, in a sense, equality.

Thus, one is forced to go to two dimensions in order to achieve this invariance. Furthermore, $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ may be negative. If one tries to add a constant to each to force positive values, one breaks the spatial invariance. Thus, spatial invariance seems to have strong consequences.

In previous notes, we examined invariance in terms of a function $f(px)f^*(px)=1$, but one does not need to consider this product in order to establish the invariance (although one can if one wishes)

At this point, ((7)) is completely mathematical. One may wish to associate a rotation with some kind of circular motion, but ((7)) holds for spin 0 particles as well as for particles with spin. One may note, however, that in a two slit interference experiment with a particle moving in the z direction $\cos(pz)$, the slits are perpendicular to z and yet should be about $1/p$ apart. Thus, the wavelength which exists in the z direction seems to exist also in a plane perpendicular to z. This suggests that there is also a physical nature to the invariance/periodicity.

Presence of a Potential

In the above section, we argued that for the statistical scenario of a free quantum particle:

$$F(p,x)= \exp(ipx) \quad ((8))$$

As a result, one has complex probability which also has positive and negative values for the real and imaginary parts. If one only had a periodic function with no invariance imposed, one could eliminate the negative portions by adding a constant i.e. $\cos(px) \rightarrow \cos(px) + B$ where $B>1$. One would then not have rotation in a circle which represents the invariance. As a result, different probabilities may add/subtract i.e. "interfere" which does not happen in classical statistical mechanics.

It may be noted, however, that adding/subtracting occurs in classical mechanics. For example, consider a rolling wheel. The overall velocity is composed of a circular velocity and a translational one. The circular velocity is constant so one has $v\cos(\omega t)$ (x unit) - $v\sin(\omega t)$ (y unit) linked to a translational velocity v (x unit) . There is overall adding or canceling in the x direction at each x, but overall there is an invariance as $E= .5I\omega\omega + .5mvv$ which is constant at all x and t.

For the quantum case of a potential, one imagines that various different momenta may be created at x stochastically i.e. one has an ensemble just as in the classical case except for the fact that the probabilities are complex and the real/imaginary parts may add/subtract i.e. interfere:

$$W(x)= \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((9))$$

Then, as written in previous notes:

$$E = \left[\sum_p \frac{p^2}{2m} a(p) \exp(ipx) \right] / \left[\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \right] + V(x) \quad ((10))$$

And:

$$\frac{p^2}{2m} a(p) \exp(ipx) + \sum_k V_k a(p-k) \exp(ipx) = E a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((11))$$

Here V_k follows from: $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$. Thus, the invariance in x remains in ((11)), but $\exp(ipx)$ becomes “dressed” with energy as it interacts with a potential which is also written in terms of periodic invariant functions through a Fourier series.

Thus, it seems that invariance is a key idea for both a free quantum particle treated statistically and one in a bound state sitting in an $\exp(ipx)$ state.

Overall Spatial Density

So far above, the term $\exp(ipx)$ has been used to describe a periodic space invariant probability of a quantum free particle. $\exp(ipx)$ depends on p and x , but is not spatial density or $P(x)$ which should be a constant. One may see that a constant follows from $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)$. If one considers ((11)), it may be summed over all p . Given that the spatial invariance is physical, one may multiply by $W^* = \sum_p a(p) \exp(-ipx)$. One may argue that this is only a mathematical procedure using orthogonal basis functions $\exp(ipx)$ to obtain an overall $\int dx W^* W KE(x) + \int dx W^* W V(x) = E$, if $\int dx W^* W$ is set to 1. Given that $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)$ yields 1, the physical spatial density for a free particle, it is tempting to call $W^*(x)W(x)$ a spatial density in the more complex case. Thus, spatial density may have humps or interference patterns due to the periodic/invariant form $\exp(ipx)$. $\exp(ipx)$ may be thought of as a conditional probability.

Superoscillations

The periodic/space invariant probability $\exp(ipx)$ holds over all space because it represents a free particle. When an ensemble is formed, various $\exp(ip_j x)$ interfere creating different shapes for $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. It is possible that $W(x)$ may become $\exp(i P x)$ in a certain x region. Thus, it appears as a periodic/invariant probability in a region, but the invariance does not hold throughout space. This happens in at least two cases: a localized bound state i.e. a particle in a well with infinite walls and superoscillations. For the particle in the infinite well, one has an exact $\cos(pave x)$ or $\sin(pave x)$ within the box, but outside the wavefunction is 0. Nevertheless, when computing the Fourier transform one must use a step function and so $a(p)$ exists for all p not just $\pm pave$.

In the case of superoscillations, it is shown in (1) that one may have a function:

$$F_n(x,a) = \{ \cos(x/n) + i a \sin(x/n) \}^n \quad ((12)) \quad a > 1$$

This may be written as a limited Fourier series i.e. depending only on some frequencies. (This occurs physically for example in optical scenarios where some light frequencies may be filtered out.)

$$F_n(x,a) = \sum_{j=0,n} C_j(a,n) \exp[(1-2j/n)ix] \quad ((13)) \quad (\text{from (1)})$$

One may see that the frequency 1 is the largest possible i.e. $(n-2j)/n$ with $j=n$ being the largest value. Choosing n large and $x=\sqrt{n}$ in ((12)) leads to $x/n = 1/\sqrt{n}$ small or

$$F_n(\sqrt{n}, a) = \{1 + i ax/n\}^n \quad ((14))$$

The limit of ((14)) for $n \rightarrow$ infinite yields $\exp(iax)$, but $a > 1$ so this is a frequency greater than 1 i.e. greater than any of its Fourier components which hold over all space.

Thus, it seems that there is localized periodic/invariance mimicking a free quantum particle as well as the global $\exp(ipx)$. If one is able to make local measurements, which one may apparently do for a particle in an infinite well, one may see the effects of a free quantum particle with a periodic/invariant probability in a localized region.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that periodicity together with invariance in space are key to obtaining $\exp(ipx)$ as the statistical probability describing a free quantum particle. We base our arguments on mimicking classical statistical mechanics. It is invariance in space which requires one to use a two vector $\exp(ipx)$. Unlike classical statistical mechanics, one may not introduce this invariance by dropping x i.e. $f(p)=\exp(-pp/2mT)$ because average kinetic energy in the case of an ensemble for a $V(x)$ is x dependent. Given that the probability depends on x , we choose a periodic function that is invariant in space i.e. equate a rotation in px ($2x^2$) to a translation in space. This leads to the form $\exp(ipx)$ as shown in Part I. We argue that although $\exp(ipx)$ is developed along mathematical lines, it seems there is physics involved as the periodicity px occurs in the direction of motion, yet a two slit interference scenario with slits about $1/p$ apart is sensitive to the wavelength in a direction transverse to the motion. $\exp(ipx)$ applies to spin 0 particles as well as spin particles so one should be careful about attributing $\exp(ipx)$ to a physical rotation, nevertheless it seems that there should be some underlying physical periodic behaviour. Furthermore, there must be some physics with establishing the idea of $1/p$ regions in space i.e. the wavelength.

A number of the ideas listed above have been mentioned in our previous notes, but here we wish to stress the idea of periodicity coupled with spatial invariance. Previously we argued that one seeks a function $f(p,x)$ such that $f^*(p,x)f(p,x)=1$ and $-id/dx f(p,x) = p f(p,x)$

References

1 Aharonov, Y. et al The Mathematics of Superoscillations (2015)
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/1511.01938.pdf>